

SYSTOLIC BLOOD PRESSURE EFFECTS DUE TO WEIGHT TRAINING ON TEENAGE VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of weight training on systolic blood pressure among volleyball players. To achieve the purpose of the present study, forty five volleyball players from Jamal Mohamed College, Tiruchirappalli, Tamilnadu, India was selected as subjects at random and their ages ranged from 18 to 21 years. The subjects (N=45) were randomly assigned to three equal groups of fifteen subjects each. The requirement of the experiment procedures, testing as well as exercise schedule was explained to the subjects so as to get full co-operation of the effort required on their part and prior to the administration of the study. Pre test was conducted for all the subjects on resting heart rate. This initial test scores formed as pre test scores of the subjects. The groups were assigned as Experimental Group I, Experimental Group II and Control Group in an equivalent manner. Experimental Group I was exposed to weight training with low volume, Experimental Group II was exposed to weight training with high volume and control group was kept at control. The duration of experimental period was 12 weeks. After the experimental treatment, all the forty five subjects were tested on resting heart rate. This final test scores formed as post test scores of the subjects. The pre test and post test scores were subjected to statistical analysis using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to find out the significance among the mean differences, whenever the 'F' ratio for adjusted test was found to be significant, scheffe's post hoc test was used. In all cases 0.05 level of significance was fixed to test hypotheses. The weight training decreased the systolic blood pressure among volleyball players.

Key Words: Yogic Practices, Plyometric, Resistance, Volleyball

Introduction:

Although some teenagers use strength training to increase muscle size for better looks, weight training is a common part of youth sports and physical fitness programs. Athletes can use their own body weight, weight machines, elastic tubing, or free weights in their strength-training regimens. Specific program goals dictate the type and quantity of weight used as well as the frequency of weight exercises. The benefits of these programs include improved performance in sports and leisure activities, decreased injuries sustained while participating in sports, increased muscle hypertrophy, a favourable improvement in body composition, lower blood pressure and lipid levels, and enhanced cardiopulmonary function. Weight training has become more and more popular lately. In addition to helping athletes improve their muscular strength, power, endurance, and hypertrophy, studies on weight training adaptations have shown benefits for both clinical and general populations (i.e., people with cardiovascular disease, neuromuscular disease, etc.) (Kraemer et al., 2002).

Methodology:

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of weight training on systolic blood pressure among volleyball players. To achieve the purpose of the present study, forty five volleyball players from Jamal Mohamed College, Tiruchirappalli, Tamilnadu, India was selected as subjects at random and their ages ranged from 18 to 21 years. The subjects (N=45) were randomly assigned to three equal groups of fifteen subjects each. The requirement of the experiment procedures, testing as well as exercise schedule was explained to the subjects so as to get full co-operation of the effort required on their part and prior to the administration of the study. Pre test was conducted for all the subjects on resting heart rate. This initial test scores formed as pre test scores of the subjects. The groups were assigned as Experimental Group I, Experimental Group II and Control Group in an equivalent manner. Experimental Group I was exposed to weight training with low volume, Experimental Group II was exposed to weight training with high volume and control group was kept at control. The duration of experimental period was 12 weeks. After the experimental treatment, all the forty five subjects were tested on resting heart rate. This final test scores formed as post test scores of the subjects. The pre test and post test scores were subjected to statistical analysis using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to find out the

significance among the mean differences, whenever the ‘F’ ratio for adjusted test was found to be significant, scheffe’s post hoc test was used. In all cases 0.05 level of significance was fixed to test hypotheses.

Results:

Computation of Mean and Analysis of Covariance on Systolic Blood Pressure of WTWLVGT, WTWHVTG and Control Group

	WTWLVGT	WTWHVTG	Control Group	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
Pre Test Mean	133.53	133.13	133.33	BG	1.20	2	0.60	0.49
				WG	50.80	42	1.21	
Post Test Mean	127.60	130.00	133.20	BG	236.80	2	118.40	56.50*
				WG	88.00	42	2.09	
Adjusted Post Test Mean	127.53	130.06	133.20	BG	240.70	2	120.35	60.04*
				WG	82.17	41	2.00	

* Significant at 0.05 level Table value for df 2, 42 was 3.21 and 2, 41 was 3.22

The above table indicates the adjusted mean value of systolic blood pressure of WTWLVGT, WTWHVTG and control group were 127.53, 130.06 and 133.20 respectively. The obtained F-ratio of 60.04 for adjusted mean was greater than the table value 3.22 for the degrees of freedom 2 and 41 required for significance at 0.05 level of confidence. The result of the study indicates that there was a significant difference among the experimental and control group on systolic blood pressure. The above table also indicates that both pre and post test means of experimental and control groups differ significantly.

The pre, post and adjusted post test mean values of systolic blood pressure of both experimental and control group are graphically represented in the figure 1.

Figure 1: Shows the Mean Values on Systolic Blood Pressure of WTWLVGT and WTWHVTG and Control Group

Table 2: Adjusted Mean and Differences between the Means of WTWLVGT, WTWHVTG and Control Group on Systolic Blood Pressure

WTWLVGT	WTWHVTG	Control Group	Mean Difference	CI Value
127.53	130.06	---	2.53*	1.31
127.53	---	133.20	5.67*	
---	130.06	133.20	3.14*	

Table 2 shows the adjusted means on systolic blood pressure and difference between the means of the WTWLVGT, WTWHVTG and control group. The mean differences of WTWLVGT and WTWHVTG, WTWLVGT and control group, WTWHVTG and control group were 2.53, 5.67 and 3.14 respectively was greater than the CI value 1.31. Hence there exist significant differences between the groups.

Conclusion:

The weight training decreased the systolic blood pressure among volleyball players.

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